

Omicron Variant : Planning for Dentists

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Now that the COVID-19 Omicron variant is rapidly spreading, dental practice needs a infection control planning immediately.

While it is true that the transmission of infectious-based agents among healthcare professionals in dentistry is considered to be rare.

Since the emergence of COVID-19 in 2019, dental facilities worldwide have made great strides in creating a strong infection control plan for their practices.

Now that the COVID-19 Omicron Variant is in full swing, it is time to take this aspect seriously. Let us know how to create a infection control plan for dentists that will keep you, your staff, and your patients safe from strain of this pandemic.

What is the COVID-19 Omicron Variant?

In November 2021, the SARS-CoV-2 variant was identified as "B.1.1.529" and quickly reported to the World Health Organization (WHO). The first two confirmed cases came out of Botswana and the South Africa region. Then it was named "Omicron". By December 2021, the first case was confirmed within the United States.

It is believed that Omicron has the capability of spreading more easily and that it may be passed from one person to another – whether symptomatic or asymptomatic, vaccinated or non vaccinated.

1. It is likely to infect individuals that have been previously vaccinated; however, it is believed that the vaccinated are at low risk for requiring hospitalization or experiencing death.

The Centres for Disease control and Prevention recommends all who are vaccinated to receive a booster per the booster vaccination schedule outlined with each vaccination.

2. It is believed that Omicron is a significantly higher threat to the immunity individuals have towards COVID-19 than that of previous variants.
3. Omicron is considered to be a highly mutated variant of COVID-19.
4. Many studies and first-hand observations seem to lean towards the fact that the illness from the Omicron variant is much milder than that of the Delta variant; however, this is not yet 100% confirmed.

Most infections that have occurred within the dental setting have been discussed as below-

1. Unsafe injection leads to transmission of infections.
2. Un sterilized dental handpieces often results in infections.
3. Finally, the contaminants that are produced during the procedures in a dental practice such as droplets of saliva, blood, dusts, aerosols, and more were found to have the single-highest impact on infectious agents appearing and being passed within dental practice.

How to Remove Contaminants in a Dental Practice?

There are several standard precautions which include-

1. Encouraging proper hand hygiene
2. Utilizing personal protective equipment
3. Practicing good hygiene
4. Placing sharps in appropriate containers
5. Sterilizing all instruments and devices
6. Disinfect all environmental surfaces

A dental aerosol control system is a specially-designed product that operates in such a manner that it removes the various types of contaminants that are created and/or caused by conducting dental procedures on patients. Examples include viruses, bacteria, dust, blood, saliva, and other components that are similar in nature. This system integrates a powerful filtration system that consists of 4 distinct layers. Not only does it absorb contaminants with nearly 100% efficiency, but when viruses and bacteria become lodged in the filtration system, the device kills them on contact.